

Quantitative and qualitative evaluation of iron VI in the compound (Na₂FeO₄) Synthesized by dry method

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Abstract

This product presents a new synthetic process of high yield, purity 95.3 to 99.1% and stable 11 months at a temperature around 25°C of Na₂FeO₄ alkaline ferrate VI. Heating the mixture of Na₂O₂ and Fe₂O₃ with the Na/Fe ratio = 3 at a temperature of 600°C for 6 hours, under the current of oxygen, in the most favourable conditions. Which is better than that synthesized by deferent synthesis pathways. The synthesis of the compound Na₂FeO₄ has been carried out under different experimental conditions (the Na/Fe ratio varies from 1 to 6, T varies between 200 – 800°C, the time varies 2 to 12h and the product storage temperature varies 15 to 35), In order to obtain an optimal yield of stable and high purity ferrate VI as well as to minimize cost, facilitate their storage and transportation and strengthen the production of iron (VI) to meet the growing demand for ferrate (VI), due to its usefulness in the purification of water and battery cathodes. The quality of the synthetic phase and the rate of degradation of iron VI after 11 months of storage at around 25°C were confirmed by different methods of analysis such as: DRX, IR spectrometry, UV spectrophotometry and by the method of volumetric titration quantitatively and qualitatively.

Keywords: Synthesis, Iron (VI), cathode, oxidizing, coagulating, purity, stability, characterization.

I. Introduction:

Recently, A. El maghraoui et coll [1], confirmed the bactericidal power of ferrate VI as a powerful disinfectant, in a study done on several pathogenic bacteria such as E. coli., Streptococcus, Shigella, Proteus, Pseudomonas sp, As well as Xiao-Nan Wu and coll [2], have demonstrated that ferrate [Fe(VI)] can effectively degrade various pollutants present in sewage.

A previous and recent study found that NaClO could react with intermediate iron species, i.e. Fe(V) and Fe (IV), to regenerate Fe(VI), which reduced unnecessary consumption of Fe (VI) by its self-decomposition and thus improved ferrate (VI) oxidability on organic substances [3].

Several previous studies have confirmed the importance of oxidation grade VI iron (Fe^{VI}O₄²⁻) as an

incredible Green Technology by their wide application as environmentally friendly oxidant, disinfectant and coagulant in water treatment and also provide multifunctional solutions in a single step, [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13].

Other studies have shown the bactericidal power of ferrate VI on the inactivation of pathogenic microorganisms such as Escherichia coli, viruses, coliforms as well as the oxidation of pharmaceutical and organic products, personal care and the removal of toxic metals [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26]. However, the synthesis of ferrates (VI) is very delicate, due to their high oxidizing power and high production costs [27], [28], [29], [30]. Although, the existence of alkaline ferrates has been cited for a century [31], [32], they have not

been the subject of a considerable number of studies, this is due to the instability and the difficulties encountered during their preparation.

More recently, A. El maghraoui et coll [33] have achieved the synthesis of a VI iron-based compound namely K_2FeO_4 , of high purity by dry by mixing potassium peroxide with Fe_2O_3 under oxygen current at a temperature of $560^\circ C$ and a K/Fe ratio equal to 4, under the most favourable conditions. Although the synthesis of iron (VI) has been studied by different authors [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40], [41], [42],[43].

According to various previous studies, the synthesis of iron (VI) by dry means lies mainly in their ability to produce alkaline ferrates (IV) or directly from cheap and readily available starting products (iron oxide), without complicated electrochemical process or preliminary preparation of reagents [44]. Martinez-tamayo et al. [45] studied the behavior of the Na_2O_2 - $FeSO_4$ system, including the results obtained using infrared spectrometry, RX diffraction and differential thermal analysis. They obtained ferrates (V) and (VI) whose nature depends on the molar ratio of the initial reagents. Kisselev et al. [46] have extensively studied the Na-Fe-O system and have shown that pure sodium ferrate (IV) of formula Na_2FeO_3 and formula Na_4FeO_5 can be prepared, they have thus obtained sodium Ferrate Na_2FeO_3 by heating the mixture of Na_2O_2 - Fe_2O_3 under oxygen to a temperature of $400^\circ C$, the molar Na/Fe ratio leading to the best results is 2.

Several authors have prepared sodium ferrate forms from Na_4FeO_5 and Na_2FeO_3 as Kopelev et al. [47] Who followed the procedure of Kisselev et al. [46]. Just as ferrates VI were synthesized from galvanized waste mixed with ferric oxide in an oven at $800^\circ C$, the sample was cooled and blended with solid sodium peroxide and then gradually heated for a few minutes [48]. That's why This process of dry ferrate preparation makes it like a green technology by recycling various iron residue compounds and prevents ferrate reaction

with water [49].

This work shows a new stable and pure ferrate VI synthesis processes in around 99 percent by dry way by optimizing the parameters influencing the yield and stability of the synthesized phase aimed at reducing the cost, facilitating transport and storage for a long time.

II. Equipment and Method

The alkaline compound Na_2FeO_4 was synthesized from the mixture of pure sodium peroxide Na_2O_2 and Fe_2O_3 of a Na/Fe ratio equal to 3 placed in a platinum heap before placing it in a oven at a temperature of $600^\circ C$ under oxygen current under the most favourable conditions, according to the reaction below (1). After 6 hours of drying, the resulting mixture is cooled in a ball dryer to retain moisture, as it is worked at a high temperature. Jiang and Lloyd [50] achieved the possibility of explosiveness of the reactive medium at a temperature greater than or equal to $500^\circ C$. Finally, with the help of a mortar and at a temperature around $25^\circ C$ (closed environment), grind the resulting product in order to store it in a vault with a temperature of $25^\circ C$.

The synthesis reaction:

The phase obtained was characterized by DRX, IR spectrometry, UV spectrophotometry and by the method of volumetric titration as well as by Mössbauer spectrometer after storage of 11 months. The high-value phase obtained according to the analyses carried out is kept at $T= 25^\circ C$ in order to track its degradation over time (test their stability), by measuring the optical density at the wavelength of 507 nm (the characteristic peak of the iron (VI) comes out at this wavelength) and at a pH greater than 10 using UV spectrophotometry, tsapin and coll. [51]. Monthly to determine the monthly degradation rate of ferrate VI (%) for 12 months of storage. However, the accuracy of the actual degradation rate of synthetic phase VI ferrates after one

year of storage is determined by volume titration and Mössbauer spectrometry.

The titration of the synthetic product by the volumetric method based on the oxidation of a chromite salt with ferrate VI determines the purities of Na₂FeO₄ between 95.3 and 99.1%, depending on the reaction below (2).

The resulting chromate is titrated with a solution of iron salt and sodium diphenylamine sulfonate as indicator [50].

The FTIR, DRX and Mössbauer spectrum of our samples were performed at the Regional University Interface Centre (CURI) in Fes, Morocco.

III. Results and discussion

1. Effect of Na/Fe ratio

The following figure (fig.1) shows the effect of the Na/Fe ratio on the evolution of the synthesis reaction of Na₂FeO₄ to optimize it from the N₂O₂ and Fe₂O₃ sodium peroxide, based on the measurement of the optical density of the ferrate (VI) solution of the phase synthesized at a wavelength of 507 nm according to the Na / Fe ratio.

Figure 1: Evolution of the optical density of the synthetic phase solution (Fe^{VI}) at 507 nm based on the Na/Fe ratio (t =6 h, T=600°C).

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the optical density of the solution of the phase Na₂FeO₄ synthesized based on the Na/Fe ratio, whose best reaction yield is fixed at the ratio 3, which is equivalent to the most interesting value of the measured optic density D.O = 3.70. This result confirms the importance of the molar ratio of the initial reagents in dry ferrate VI synthesis demonstrated by Martinez-tamayo et coll [45].

2. Effect of temperature

The results of the effect of the calcination temperature on the yield of the reaction of sodium peroxide N₂O₂ and Fe₂O₃ are shown in Figure 2 below at a temperature range of 200 to 800°C).

Figure 2: Evolution of the optical density of the solution of the synthesized phase at 507 nm depending on the temperature (Na/Fe =3, t=6 h).

The optical density reaches its peak at a value of 3.7 at a temperature of 600°C and beyond, it begins to decrease which means that the yield of the synthetic reaction of iron VI reached are maximum at around 600 °C. Hence the importance of optimizing the

temperature during the synthesis of this iron-based compound VI by dry means..

3. Effect of calcination time

Figure 3 shows the change in the yield of the dry ferrate VI synthesis reaction under exclusive conditions depending on the drying time.

Figure 3: Evolution of the optical density of the synthesized phase solution at 507 nm in time (Na/Fe =3, T=600°C)

According to Figure 3, the optical density reaches the value of 3.7 during a 6 h heating period and after that time it begins to decrease, which means that the yield of the synthetic reaction of the achieved iron VI are maximum at around 6 hours. Hence the importance of optimizing the time during the synthesis of ferrates VI by dry way.

4. Synthetic phase durability

The results of ferrate VI stability in time are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Evolution of the optical density of the synthesized phase solution at 507 nm based on storage months at a temperature of 25°C.

Figure 4 shows that the optical density measured every month after storage at a temperature of around 25°C is constant until about 11 months and after that time it begins to decrease slightly, which means that the rate of degradation of iron VI in the different months remains unchanged until month 11. Indeed, this result shows a progress in the synthesis of ferrate VI stable at a temperature of around 25°C, such that one of the tips related to iron VI is due to their instability [38], [39].

The degradation rate of ferrate (VI) is presented by the following formula:

$$\% \text{ of ferrate degradation VI} = \frac{D. O_i - D. O_f}{D. O_i}$$

D. O_i and D. O_f:

Optical density of ferrate VI

The following table shows the results of the calculation of the percentage degradation of ferrate VI of the synthesized phase between the different months, as well as the percent of degrade between the state of synthesis of ferrates VI and the various months after storage at a temperature of around 25 °C.

Table 1: Evolution of the optical density of synthetic ferrate VI Na_2FeO_4 in terms of the percentage of degradation between the state of synthesis and each month of the storage of ferrate VI (%) as well as percentages of degrade between the months of this phase of storage (%).

Month	The percentage of degradation between the synthesis state and the months of storage of ferrate VI (%)	The percentage of ferrate VI degradation each month (%)
1	0.02	0.02
2	0.02	0.00
3	0.05	0.03
4	0.05	0.00
5	0.06	0.01
6	0.06	0.00
7	0.06	0.00
8	0.07	0.01
9	0.07	0.00
10	0.08	0.01
11	0.08	0.00
12	0.21	0.10

According to table 1, the degradation percentage is unchanged near ferrate VI until 11 months after storage and varies in a differential manner from month to month when stored at 25°C. This means that this degradation may be due to the low level of impurities detected in the synthesized phase, however, the percentage of degrade observed between the different months of storage at a temperature of around 25°C does not exceed 0.01 % and is limited to 0.06% in the first six months, and not exceeds 0.08% in the 11th month after storage. That is why the results obtained can solve the problem of stability of ferrate VI at a well-defined temperature. Despite the studies on the synthesis of ferrates VI by dry pathway remain insufficient compared to other methods of synthetic which makes negative on the improvement of this type of synthesis, which is beneficial to the environment as it can be considered as green technology for the recycling of various iron residue compounds as well as to decrease the cost of the synthetics of this super oxidant directly from cheap and easily available starting product (iron oxide) and above all iron VI presents the future of water treatment as oxidative coagulant and

disinfectant and also used as a battery cathode thanks to their high potential and their capacity to store electric charges. However, the problem of explosiveness remains a barrier that demands to develop it and especially in the dry way works at a high temperature above 400°C which can make explosive according to Kisselev et al [46].

III. Characterization and analysis

1. RX diffraction (DRX)

The diffractometer used is the computer-driven XPERT-PRO with a $\text{K}\alpha$ copper cathode ($\lambda = 1.5405980$). Scan adopted with a step of 0.06682° and a time/no of 1s. The angular range of measurement is 10° to 80° . Figure 5 shows the X-ray diffractogram obtained on potassium ferrate powder for a ratio of ($\text{Na}/\text{Fe} = 1, 2, 3$) and calcined at 600°C for 6h. The RX diffractogram presents a mixture of ferrate (VI) characteristic reflections peaks (Licht, 2001) [36] of different purity depending on the ratio (Na/Fe) used. Furthermore, some phase peaks that can be assimilated to intermediate compounds of iron IV or V for the $\text{Na}/\text{Fe} = 1$ or 2 ratios located around 2 theta equals 33

and 36, such that the angle of these peaks does not represent the iron III used at the beginning. However, the characteristic peaks of iron VI are found to be net at 2 theta equal to 24.7; 25.5; 30.2; 39.8; 45.4 and 55.5 for the Na/Fe ratio = 3 (fig.5) which is compatible with those found by deferent authors [35], [36], [37], [38]. The minor differences observed for certain peaks can be attributed to the process of sampling and calibration, as well as to the types of reagents used. Indeed, the result observed in DRX confirms the degree of purity obtained by UV spectrometer and by volumetric titration.

Figure 5: DRX spectra of three samples of Na_2FeO_4 synthesized with Na/Fe ratio = 1, 2 and 3

2. IR Spectrometry

IR spectroscopy is a quantitative method to prove the existence of Iron (VI) in the synthesized phase. Because the appearance of the spectrum is related to the symmetry of the FeO_4^{2-} molecule or groups (tetrahedral structure), the IR spectrum of potassium powders calcinated at 600°C for 6h was recorded in a wavelength range ranging from 500 cm^{-1} to 1600 cm^{-1} . The IR spectrum of raw powders (Fig. 6) presents a series of absorption bands marked by absorptive bands located at $767, 781, 790, 807, 990$ and 1150 cm^{-1} characteristic of ferrate (VI) and has a great similarity to those found by the authors C. Li et al. [42]; W. Griffith [52]; P. Tarte et al. [53]. However, the

vibration band at 1500 cm^{-1} can be attributed to phase Na_2O clusters, thus confirming the results obtained by DRX.

Figure 6: IR Spectrometer of Na_2FeO_4 synthesized with Na/Fe ratio = 3.

3. Volumetric analysis

The percentage of the purity of the synthetic phase Na_2FeO_4 for a Na/Fe = 3 ratio and calcinated at 600°C for 6 h, is limited between 95.3% to 99.1% based on the redox state and the remaining iron is in a weaker state of valence, after the chromium analysis according to the method of Lee Y.H. et coll (2004) [49]. Although at these relatively low concentration levels, the specific nature of this ferric impurity is difficult to distinguish, but it can be attributed to intermediate iron IV or V compounds. Because the absorption bands observed on the IR spectrometer do not represent any symmetry of the molecule that presents the grade III iron used in the initial reagents. Indeed, this result is consistent with those obtained by IR spectroscopy, DRX and UV spectrophotometer. In any case, it can be assumed that excess iron, existing in several forms of amorphous iron salts can be generalized in the form of an impurity of the intermediate compounds of iron IV or V to 0.7%.

4. Mössbauer spectroscopy

Mössbauer spectroscopy in particular allows a quantitative analysis of the oxidation states of iron, because it is very sensitive to the environment of the

resonant nucleus and also allows to highlight the existence of a magnetic order at low temperature, generating six transitions that gives rise to a sextuple in the case of iron [35], [55],[56]. The characterization of the synthetic phase Na_2FeO_4 by Mössbauer spectroscopy after 11 months of storage at a temperature of around 25°C , reveals no significant degradation of Iron(VI) over time (fig. 7). In fact, the spectrum is presented in the form of an enlarged magnetic component which has been calculated by the superposition of the sextuplet and a paramagnetic compound adjusted by a paramagnetic doublet. The hyperfine parameters derived from the sound spectrum calculation are grouped in the table below. Table 2: Hyper-fine parameters derived from spectrum calculation after 10 months of storage at a temperature of around 25°C .

H_{hyp} = champ hyperfin. A = poids de la composante en % du spectre total.

	Composante élargie			Composante paramagnétique		
	Sextuplet 2			Doublet		
	H_{hyp} (kOe)	ISO (mm/s)	A (%)	ΔEQ (kOe)	ISO (mm/s)	A (%)
E_5	985	0.03	96.4	0.093	0.05	3.1

The hyperfine parameters deduced from the spectrum calculation after 11 months of storage at a temperature of around 25°C , allows to visualize the degree of iron oxidation and know the evolution of the iron level (VI) over time, because the trick linked to ferrate VI is due to its instability over time. According to the results (Table. 2 and Fig. 7), it is observed that the degradation of iron VI translates into the spectrum by an isomeric shift of 0.03 mm/s for the sextuplet which presents iron (VI) and which comes out near -1 [35], [55],[56]. This confirms the result found by DRX, IR spectrometer, chromium analysis and UV spectrometers. This isomeric shift is due to a low degradation of Iron (VI) into Iron (III) related to the processing method or where a low percentage of

impurity remains in the sample and is limited by chromium analysis to 0.7%.

Figure 7: Mössbauer Na_2FeO_4 Spectrometer after 10 months of storage at 25°C .

The volumetric titration method limits the degradation rate of iron VI after 11 months of storage to 0.07%, confirming the results found by the Mössbauer spectrometer and UV spectrophotometry. This result is a step forward in the synthesis of stable iron VI by dry way in order to facilitate its storage and transportation. As well as dry synthesis remains easy, without electrochemical complication and preparation of reagents because it relies only on the recycling of iron waste which is rather available and cheaper.

V. DISCUSSION

According to our results, the synthesis of ferrates VI including Na_2FeO_4 by stable dry way for 11 months of storage at a temperature of 25°C and of purity ranging from 95.3 to 99.1% requires a Na/Fe = 3 ratio (Fig. 1) under the most favourable conditions ($T=600^\circ\text{C}$ for 6h of drying) under oxygen current (fig. 2, 3, 4). This is compatible with the results of various preliminary studies [45], [46], showing the effect of the ratio of reagents on dry iron (VI) synthesis.

Kopelev and coll [47] achieved the effect of the heating temperature of the reactive mixture on the yield and purity of the dry phase synthesized by mixing the waste with ferric oxide in a oven at 800°C , which is compatible with our results obtained at 600°C . Another preliminary study by Martinez-tamayo et al. [45] showed the behavior of the $\text{Na}_2\text{O}_2\text{-FeSO}_4$ system by

heating it to a temperature of 400°C and under the current of oxygen to synthesize pure ferrate VI. However, this view is only suitable for drying in a temperature range of less than or equal to 400 °C, because in reality, and at temperatures above 400°C, Na₂O₂ is better for dry preparation of Fe(VI) under oxygen current and with a Na/Fe=3 molar ratio than Na₂O. Despite the insufficient studies done on the synthesis of ferrates by dry means, due to the use of a high temperature and which can lead to explosiveness. But whatever this method resides more interesting for the ability to produce alkaline ferrates (VI) or directly from cheap and readily available starting product (iron oxide), and to avoid the complicated electrochemical procedure of preliminary preparation of reagents [44]. According to our results, 6 hours of heating of the reactionary mixture of Na₂O₂ with Fe₂O₃ have sufficient at a temperature of 600°C, under oxygen current to the maximum yield of the synthetic reaction of pure ferrate VI at 99.1% and stable at 25°C. This time means that the synthesis reaction goes through several stages in order to stabilize Iron VI, i.e. iron III used as starting reagents can go through several intermediate compounds of degree of oxidation IV and V to reach the degree of Oxidation VI. This is compatible with studies by Martinez-tamayo et al. [45] and Kisselev et al. [46]. These studies have shown that they may have obtained ferrates (V) and (VI) whose nature depends on the molar ratio of initial reagents, and Cici. M et al. [48] reached the synthesis of ferrate VI by heating the ferric oxide and sodium peroxide mixture for a few minutes at 800°C in several phases. Several previous studies have shown that the dry ferrate VI synthesis method remains the most advantageous compared to other synthesizing methods, in order to avoid the complications of the electrochemical pathway process and the reaction of ferrates with water as well as their ability to produce VI ferrates in quantity to meet the growing global demand. The availability of iron oxides as a starting product can

be found easily and inexpensively, which makes the cost of synthesis positive and raises demand worldwide [44], [49]. As a result, the pics found by DRX (fig. 5), show a great similarity with those found by different authors [40], [41], [42], [43]. However, there are some minor discrepancies that may be due to different methods of sampling and calibration. The absorption bands that illustrate the symmetry of the FeO₄²⁻ molecule or groupings (tetrahedral structure), observed on the IR spectrometer (fig. 6), present a great similarity with that of the previous authors C. Li et al. [42]; W. Griffith [52]; P. Tarte et al. [53] and confirms the different results of the analyses obtained. However, due to the effectiveness and availability of UV spectrometer, it has been widely used to test different experimental conditions (Na/Fe = 1 – 6, T = 200 – 800°C, t = 2 – 12h and at product storage temperature (T = 15 - 35), by measuring the optical density of the ferrate solution (VI) at the 507 nm wavelength that determines the existence of iron VI [51].

The positive results obtained by UV spectrometer were confirmed by DRX, IR spectrometers and volumetric titration analysis (% of phase purity found). The Mössbauer spectrometer has been used only to confirm the existence of iron VI after 11 months of storage at a temperature of 25°C (fig. 7), based on its reliability to reveal the different degrees of iron oxidation that exists in the phase, therefore to give a further idea about the rate of

iron degradation VI and the type of iron thus formed.

According to our results, the degradation rate of synthetic ferrate VI does not exceed 0.07% after 11 months of storage, which represents an incredible progress in the synthesis of ferrates VI by a dry pathway.

The availability of different sources of ferric oxides (galvanized waste, feric oxides..) as a starting product that may have found easily and inexpensive, makes positive on the cost of synthesis and raises the demand

worldwide, As the syntheses of ferrates VI by dry way avoids the problem of formulation and preparation of reagents and electrochemical complications [44], [49].

VI. Conclusion

This article reviews the most appropriate method for the synthesis of ferrate (VI) Na_2FeO_4 stable at a temperature around 25°C by dry way, using the direct reaction of the mixture of Fe_2O_3 with Na_2O_2 in the most favourable experimental conditions so far (Na/Fe ratio = 3, a temperature of 600°C for 6 hours under current of oxygen). The dry ferrate (VI) synthesis method is a very easy

VII. References

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